

THE IMPORTANCE OF NURSING IN FAMILY MEDICINE

Salixodjayeva Rixsiniso Kamilovna

Center for the development of professional qualifications of medical personnel, head of the department, dotsent

Axunova Nilufar Xusanovna

Alimova Fatima Zakirovna

Tojiboyeva Gulnora Sheraliyevna

Center for the development of professional qualifications of medical personnel, assistant

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8176560>

Abstract: Nurses are considered as one of the members of family physician teams, therefore it is important to explain the role of nurses in it. The aim of study was to determination of nurses' roles in the family physician team. This article provides information on the importance of nurses in family medicine.

Keywords: nurses, patient care team, family physician's team, attitude of health personnel

In recent years, society has felt everything greater interest in health issues. It is caused primarily by a deterioration in the quality of life population. Center for the application of the forces of medicine as scientific and practical industry should be not only sick, but also a fully healthy person, protection and strengthening of his health. The only real way to solve health problems is prevention. Preventive medicine plays a fundamental role in maintaining and promoting family health and increasing life expectancy. Family physician team is responsible for the delivery of comprehensive care services for individuals and families of different age and sex. The performance of family physician depends on team's familiarity with the patient and the community and it puts emphasis on the prevention of diseases and promotion of health. As defined by the WHO, the main goal of the family physician plan is to provide comprehensive and continuous care for people, with a special focus on the family and community

Of all the participants, 30 persons (20%) were male and the rest were female (80%). The findings of the study reported based on the mean score of five. The collected data indicated that the nurses participating in the study, as a member of family physician team, had a tendency to take part in the following activities: support (4.44), care (4.37), management (4.05), counseling (3.93), prevention (3.81), and education (3.78).

Thus, for the development of family medicine, a sharp activation of the nursing link of the general practice team is necessary. A competent general practice nurse is able to take over most of the preventive, health education and thus significantly relieve the family doctor. But here Don't forget the low wages nurse, which is one of the main reasons for the outflow of nursing personnel from medicine. Another issue that needs to be addressed is legal support for nurses providing legitimacy of its independent activity. Further progress in family medicine, which is the main form of organization PHC is not realistic without addressing these issues as soon as possible problems.

Doctor to open vital signs instructions are not required. The nurse assesses the general condition of the patient to assess his pulse, body temperature and breathing can measure at will. However, if the patient's condition is serious, the doctor shows the main indicators

instructs to measure frequently. From a surgical operation then, during the recovery phase, measure vital signs It is performed in 15 minutes until the patient's condition is stable. Do this every hour in a patient with a high temperature. If such a patient is prescribed an antipyretic, his turn on the temperature every 30 minutes to determine the effect. An electronic thermometer is attached to the device follow the manufacturer's instructions. Always the temperature a clean hard plastic case is used for measurement. Temperature put the meter in the case and the bottle in the patient's mouth place as described in the case of the thermometer. 30 – 50 after a second, the temperature indicator will appear on the instrument display. Then press the button on the thermometer to eject the case press At this pressure, the thermometer is ready for further use will automatically reset to . Electronic when the patient's temperature is reduced when using a thermometer whether he sits with his mouth open or closed depends on the accuracy of the indicators has a minimal effect. If the temperature of the electronic thermometer of a thermometer if used for rectal (in the rectum) measurement that the end (leg) that is inserted into the mouth is inserted into the rectum replaceable, closed with a disposable case. From the use of the case it is lubricated before and discarded after use.

To collect the data, a researcher-made questionnaire was designed and prepared by the researcher based on scientific resources, manuals, and executive guidelines. The questionnaire designed based on of the official duties of professional nurses in Iran. In addition, the research team used theirs many years academic and practical experience in various areas of health care, scientific documents and resources to design the questionnaire. This questionnaire was consisted of two parts: the first part had 10 questions about demographic characteristics and history of attending education courses; the second part included a list of 54 questions that covered the tasks that a nurse could take. Using the Likert scale, there were three options for each question, including: agree, no opinion, and disagree.

Obviously, in order to make coordination in a group, it is of great importance to define and accept the role of any individual in the group; the position and role of each team member must be accepted by the person taking the role, as well as by other individuals in the team. Therefore, since the presence of nurses in the family physician, team is a new experience in developing country's health systems and for the nursing staff as well, conducting new studies can help to provide a more accurate explanation of the status and position of the team members, including nurses, and can provide a ground for achieving success. Thus, this study was conducted to determine the preference of nurses about their role in family physician team. In addition to personal interests and organizational variables, it seems other variables such as gender and work experience could be influential in the tendency to different roles of nurses. Therefore, the effect of these factors on the preferential role of nurses in the family physician team has also been considered.

In the present study, the tendency of nurses to play a supportive role is considered as a positive factor and is in line with the results of other studies that highlighted the comprehensiveness of the roles and some studies introduced models for increase effectiveness of advocacy and supportive in health intervention . However, nurses tendency to play the role of care suggests that nurses tend to play the roles in the family physicians team, which they have experienced during many years of activity in hospitals and health care facilities. In line with the results of the present study, the results of a study which investigated and clarified the general roles and capabilities of family nurses (FP-RNs) showed that nurses

should distinguish between care services for the family and acute care services provided in the intensive care unit. The nurse monitors the depth and character of breathing and should be described. Respiratory and metabolic diseases, as well as other acute and chronic medical problems of breathing may cause a change. Sometimes chest sides can rise and fall symmetrically. "Dyspnea" the term is used to designate other difficulties in breathing possible. The relative tendency of nurses participating in the present study toward managerial roles is promising; however, it is necessary to enhance their individual preparedness and legal frameworks as well. It is even believed that nurses can play a role in policymaking and even financial management in different areas of health system

Conclusion: The results of the study showed that the nurses were more interested in playing a role in supporting and caring for patients, rather than participating in education and preventive activities. Since family physician teams must mainly provide community-based preventive services, the authorities should try to enhance the interests and capabilities of nurses to empower them to play a role in preventive and education activities.

References:

1. S.A.Mukhina, I.I.Tarnovskaya. Atlas po maniplyatsionnoy tekhnische sestriinskogo ukhoda. - ANMI, 1995.
2. M.A. Fozilbekova, N.A. Nurmatova. Nursing theory basics. - "O teacher", 2002.
3. Q.S. Inamov. Fundamentals of Nursing. - T., 2007.
4. T.I.Umarova, M.A.Qayumova, M.Q.Ibrahimova. Nursing work - T., "Zarqalam", 2005..

